

PLANTATION STUDIES

Volume 1

Proceedings of the
3rd International Symposium on
One Health, One World (OHOW2024)

10 - 12 December 2024
Putrajaya, Malaysia

UPM
UNIVERSITI PUTRA MALAYSIA
BERILMU BERAKTIF

EXPLORING THE SURFACE WATER STATUS OF AWD IRRIGATED RICE PADDY FIELDS INTEGRATING SAR-UAV AND IOT TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION

MD RAHEDUL ISLAM^{1*} and WATARU TAKEUCHI²

¹ Department of Geography and Environment, Pabna University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh

² Institute of Industrial Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

*Correspondence: rahe_ge@pust.ac.bd

Keywords: Synthetic Aperture Radar, Time series, Backscatter, Machine learning, Bangladesh

RESEARCH SUMMARY

Alternate wetting and drying (AWD) is a proven technique to reduce irrigated water, and methane emissions without yield reduction of rice cultivation. The effective and efficient ways to monitor paddy field surface water are significant to successfully implementing AWD to reduce water use and methane emissions. The aim of the study to monitoring AWD water status of rice paddy fields with remotely sensed data, Unnamed Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and IoT based low-cost water level monitoring devices. The experiment fields design with installation of IoT based water level devices and periodically UAV flight at the selected six plots in Bangladesh.

The vertically VV (vertical-vertical) polarization data, in comparison to VH (vertical-horizontal) polarization, show high sensitivity to soil moisture (Patel et al., 2006). The VH data, in its turn, has a higher sensitivity to volume scattering, which depends strongly on the geometrical alignment and characteristics of the vegetation. Thus, VH data has a limited potential for the estimation of soil moisture compared to VV data, but higher sensitivity to vegetation (Eweys et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2018; Gherboudj et al., 2011). As soil moisture of rice paddy field depends on irrigation, we use both VV and VH polarization data. In case of temporal resolution is very important to observe the AWD cycle, high temporal resolution required.

As a result, we used both ascending and descending data of the study area and the resolution becomes 3-7 days. Moreover, we used UAV flight to increases the high temporal observation in case of SAR images absence. The dataset has been collected from rice growing and AWD cycle practicing time from February to April 2024. The result found that the low cost IoT device-based water level data of six experimental field and farmer level manual data are good agreement. The AWD irrigation cycle varied based on the different agroclimatic variables.

The sensor-based detection also observed such variation like the maximum (06 times) AWD cycle duration observed in Naldanga, Natore district and minimum (04 times) in Pabna district. The AWD cycle length also varied as the maximum (8-10 days)

duration at Pabna and shortest duration (03-05) at Naldanga, Natore district. In Figure 1, the IoT device and device-based water level data showed with the clear irrigation cycle of the AWD irrigation schedule.

In case of SAR database water status monitoring case, the backscatter's coefficient value of VV and VH compared with water level data. The VV values are less sensitive than the VH value to watered condition of the rice paddy field. In Figure 2(a) shows the VV value fluctuate with response of the water level status. Similarly, in Figure 2(b) showed the variation of VH value fluctuated with water level condition. In the phase irrigated condition are comparatively more sensitive than the dry condition of the rice paddy field. The VV and VH both values slightly reduced and less responsive to IoT based water level data as the rice paddy growth stage, the canopy height and vegetation density increased.

Figure 1. Low cost IoT sensor based (left) water level monitoring device, and (right) water level data to monitor AWD irrigation practices

Figure 2. Low cost IoT sensor-based water level data (cm) comparison with SAR backscattered coefficient Sigma0 (left) VV (dB), (right) VH (dB)

This study provides a new paradigm for monitoring the water status of rice fields, which will be key to the precision irrigation of paddy fields in large regions in the future. As well as the accurate irrigated and non-irrigated conditions of rice paddy fields will help to monitoring AWD implantation and greenhouse gasses emission.

THE IMPACT OF LAND USE/COVER CHANGES ON HABITAT QUALITY IN JOHOR RIVER BASIN, MALAYSIA

Y.S. YONG¹ and K.D. KANNIAH^{2,3*}

¹Faculty of Built Environment & Surveying, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia,

²Tropical Map Research Group, Faculty of Built Environment & Surveying, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia,

³Centre for Environmental Sustainability and Water Security (IPASA), Research Institute for Sustainable Environment, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia,

*Correspondence: kasturi@utm.my

Keywords: *Habitat quality, River basins, InVEST, Malaysia*

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing benefits delivered by biodiversity to human welfare, essential living resources, and the global economy highlight its importance for human development [1,2]. Biodiversity encompasses not only the diversity of living organisms at the genetic and species levels but also the variety of ecosystem services—such as provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural services—provided by these organisms [1,3]. Unfortunately, the growing anthropogenic pressures on natural habitats are expected to exceed previous levels and continue rising in the future [4,5]. One of the major outcomes of anthropogenic activities is Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) change [6]. Human-induced landscape alterations driven by economic or political forces have significant impacts on key components of the Earth system, modifying habitat structure and disrupting the circulation of materials and the flow of energy between habitat patches [1,7]. Consequently, LULC change is a major risk factor for habitat quality (HQ). However, few studies have modeled the impact of LULC change on HQ. This study, therefore, focuses on the Johor River Basin (JRB) to explore the potential of using remote sensing approaches to model HQ in this region [8,9].

The JRB is one of Malaysia's most vital basins, both economically and for supplying natural resources to two metropolitan areas [10,11]. It is the primary source of freshwater for the southern Johor region and partially serves Singapore. However, Kang and Kanniah suggest that rapid changes in the JRB and its surrounding areas are primarily driven by fast-paced economic development and population growth [7]. Although anthropogenic activities, such as the construction of dams and barrages along the JRB, were intended to improve human welfare, they have severely degraded the ecological environment [12,13]. Therefore, the anthropogenic pressures within the JRB are considered a significant threat to the habitat stability of the river basin.

One approach to effective river basin management is the use of Decision Support Systems (DSSs), which can help managers protect the environment [1,14]. DSSs can be supported by indicators of ecosystem health and biological sustainability, such as habitat quality (HQ), which reflects the spatial relationship between ecological quality and human-induced threats [15,16]. HQ studies are typically conducted through two approaches: (1) field measurements of biodiversity, and (2) ecological process modeling and simulation [17]. Malaysia's unique geographical characteristics and accessibility challenges have limited field-based HQ studies. Therefore, modeling approaches are necessary to assess HQ in the JRB in relation to LULC changes [8,9].

In this study, HQ is estimated using the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST) model, which is widely used by researchers due to its broad applicability and the ability to provide high predictive accuracy with minimal data requirements [18]. Additionally, InVEST allows for spatial visualization of results, enhancing the understanding of outcomes [15,19]. The LULC data for the JRB and associated threat sources over the past 20 years were applied to the InVEST model to simulate changes in HQ related to LULC alterations. Increasing threats in areas of interest—such as population growth, agricultural expansion, and cultural transformation—have the potential to diminish ecosystem services in the JRB [10].

This study aims to help decision-makers better understand the conditions of habitat quality in the study area. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to: (1) analyze changes in habitat quality in the JRB from 2000 to 2020; (2) present spatiotemporal responses of HQ to LULC changes and impact factors; and (3) compare HQ responses with and without the presence of protected areas.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Johor is the second-largest state in the southern part of Peninsular Malaysia. The Johor River Basin as shown in Figure 1 is in the southeast of Johor (1.426°–2.080°N, 103.330°–104.075°E). It originates from Gunung Belumut, stretches for approximately 122.7km, and covers a water area of about 2,63km². The Johor River flows in a north-south direction toward the Straits of Johor, with the Lingui Dam serving as its main reservoir. Several major rivers are located within the basin, including the Sayong River, Linggui River, Tiram River, Semanggar River, Layang River, and Lebam River [20]. Malaysia has an equatorial climate, and the Johor River Basin experiences tropical monsoon influences, receiving rainfall throughout the year [21]. The primary land use and land cover (LULC) types in the basin are natural forests, followed by agricultural areas (oil palm and rubber plantations). Part of the river basin lies within Iskandar Malaysia, which has been undergoing rapid development since 2006 [3]. The major LULC transformations in the basin, driven by increasing urbanization and agricultural expansion, aim to accommodate population growth and meet the economic demands of the industrial and agricultural sectors.

Figure 1. Johor river basin boundary containing river and protected areas

2.2 Data Sources and Processing

The LULC maps used in this study for the years 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, and 2020 were obtained from a previous study conducted by Kang and Kanniah, which examined land use changes and alterations in river morphology within the Johor River Basin [7]. Six LULC classes were identified in the basin, based on the local land use map provided by the National Land Use Information Division, Department of Town and Country Planning, Malaysia. The *Kappa coefficients* for all land-use classifications from 2000 to 2020 are

greater than 85%, and therefore, the classifications are considered reliable for this study.

The remaining data required for model input are shown in Table 1. The socio-economic data presented in Table 1 represent key sources of negative impacts on habitat quality. These data were used as input raster layers for the threat sources affecting habitat quality in the study area. The respective impact weights and distances of these threats were adjusted based on expert knowledge and findings from similar studies. Environmental data, such as the digital elevation model (DEM), were used to generate elevation and slope information for the study area. These physical and geographical factors were then utilized as variables for correlating with the habitat quality scores generated later in the study.

Table 1. Source of model input

Type	Information	
	Name	Source
Environmental data	Digital Elevation Model	Department of Survey and Mapping Malaysia
Socio-economic data	Population Density	WorldPop
	Building Extent	
	Nighttime Lights	
	Roadmap	OpenStreetMap
	Protected Areas	World Database on Protected Areas

2.3 InVEST Model

InVEST is an open-source software model developed by the U.S. Natural Capital Project Team to map and value the goods and services from nature that sustain human life [15,22]. One of the models included in the software is the Habitat Quality Model that has been utilized in this study. The HQ is suitable for the measurement of anthropogenic impacts on the ecological environment; thus, the degree of habitat degradation was assessed through habitat suitability of different LULC types (H) and the sensitivity of LULC to external threat factors (D), with calculation from the HQI (Q) formulation [22] below:

$$Q_{xj} = H_j \left(1 - \left(\frac{D_{xj}^z}{D_{xj}^z + k^z} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

where Q_{xj} and D_{xj} represent the HQI and degree of habitat degradation (total threat level) respectively at grid x in the LULC type j ; H_j is each LULC category assigned with a habitat score from 0 to 1 (1 = highest habitat suitability, 0 = no habitat); z

is an empirical model constant of 2.5 and k are scaling parameters (or constants).

Habitat degradation was assessed from the formulation below:

$$D_{xj} = \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{y=1}^{Y_r} \left(\frac{w_r}{\sum_{r=1}^R w_r} \right) r_y i_{rxy} \beta_x S_{jr} \quad (2)$$

where R represents the index of all modeled degradation sources; Y_r is the set of grid cells for threat r 's raster maps; y indicates the index of all grid cells on r 's raster map; w_r is the weight parameters; β_x is the accessibility factor.

The InVEST model utilizes a half-saturation curve to show the correlation between habitat degradation scores and habitat quality scores, therefore threat decay is assigned as either a linear or exponential distance-decay function.

The impact of threat (i_{rxy}) was assessed from the formulation below:

$$i_{rxy} = 1 - \left(\frac{d_{xy}}{d_{r \max}} \right) \text{ if linear} \quad (3)$$

$$i_{rxy} = \exp \left(- \left(\frac{2.99}{d_{r \max}} \right) d_{xy} \right) \text{ if exponential} \quad (4)$$

where d_{xy} indicates the distance between raster x and y ; $d_{r \max}$ shows the maximum distance of threat r acts.

The threat sources in this study were analyzed with a raster calculator tool through ArcGIS 10.8., and LULC-Threat sensitivities were determined from the InVEST model user's guide [22] and referred to similar studies [1,10,23].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Land Use/Cover Change Analysis

The LULC data for the Johor River Basin (JRB) generated by Kang and Kanniah for the years 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, and 2020 had Kappa values of 0.955, 0.886, 0.914, 0.940, and 0.957, respectively [7]. These values indicate significant LULC changes in the JRB over the twenty-year period. According to the previous study, the LULC in 2000 was dominated by agricultural land (68.1%), forest (20.7%), water (5.8%), and urban areas (2.3%) [7]. By 2020, urban and water land types had increased to 4.4% and 6.6%, respectively, due to residential expansion, while forest and agricultural land types had decreased to 19.0% and 67.7%, respectively. Particularly concerning is the mangrove land type, which covered less than 2.0% of the study area in 2000; over the past twenty years, nearly 30% of this area has been lost. These changes highlight a significant reduction in habitat-suitable land types, such as forests and mangroves, with a conversion to urban and water land types.

3.2 Habitat Quality Assessment

Changes in LULC and threat source density can directly or indirectly affect ecosystem stability. In

this study, habitat quality and degradation scores are used as quantitative measures to assess changes in ecosystem stability within the study area.

3.3 Changes in Habitat Quality

The spatial-temporal analysis of habitat quality (HQ) over 20 years in the Johor River Basin (JRB), shown in Figure 2, reveals a slight decrease in HQ from 2000 to 2020. From 2000 to 2015, HQ decreased from 0.2474 to 0.2353. However, it increased to 0.2417 from 2015 to 2020, resulting in an overall reduction in HQ from 0.2474 to 0.2417. A notable change in HQ was observed in 2015, likely due to the significant land use changes that occurred between 2010 and 2015. During this period, forest cover was converted into other land types, such as bare soil and agricultural land, leading to decreased habitat suitability in the study area [3]. Similar findings were reported by Zhang et al. (2024), who noted a gradual decline in HQ in the southern part of the Johor River due to land transformation from natural habitat to construction land [10]. The rapid land changes between 2010 and 2015 may have been driven by the development of the Iskandar Malaysia region, which had negative impacts on HQ [3]. Additionally, the loss of water bodies in 2015, particularly due to drought conditions associated with the El Niño climate phenomenon, contributed to the decline in HQ [3,24]. Water bodies, forests, and mangroves are land types with the highest habitat quality in the study area, so the reduction in forest cover and water bodies in 2015 resulted in the lowest HQ scores for the Johor River Basin. On the other hand, the increase in HQ in 2020 compared to 2015 can be attributed to the changes in LULC during the five-year interval. Between 2016 and 2020, the construction of the Seluyut Dam within JRB led to a significant conversion of other land types into water bodies, which improved HQ scores [25]. Additionally, forest cover in 2020 showed a net gain compared to its loss, further reducing the habitat degradation score for that year.

Figure 2. The JRB habitat quality score graph comparison for different years

3.4 Correlation of Impact Factor to Habitat Quality

The impact factors, such as physio-geographical factors (elevation, slope) and anthropogenic

activities (population density, building extent), were applied to statistical analysis (R 4.4.1) to identify their influence on the spatial patterns of habitat quality in the river basin. The results indicated that elevation was significantly correlated with the distribution of habitat quality scores ($p \leq 0.01$) in the Johor River Basin (JRB) over 20 years, as shown in Table 2. The uniform elevation and gentle slopes in the southwestern part of the river basin provided an opportunity for agricultural development, which influenced both LULC distribution and the corresponding habitat quality scores [26]. Population density, on the other hand, was found to have a significant correlation with habitat quality for the reference years ($r_{2020} = -0.33$, $r_{2015} = -0.23$, $r_{2000} = -0.31$, $p \leq 0.01$), but a non-significant correlation for 2010 and 2005 ($r_{2010} = -0.16$, $r_{2005} = -0.17$), indicating that anthropogenic activities increasingly impacted the fragmentation of biodiversity and habitat quality within the river basin. Furthermore, due to high elevation, rising slopes, and the implementation of protected areas, habitat suitability was relatively high in the northeastern part of the study area. The Panti, Seluyut, Kluang, and Ulu Sedili Water Catchment Forests, located in this area, contributed to conserving biodiversity and creating a favourable habitat.

Table 2. Correlation coefficient of impact factors and habitat quality from different years

Year	Impact Factors			
	Elevation	Population Density	Slope	Building Extent
2020	0.59**	-0.33**	0.37**	-0.23*
2015	0.48**	-0.23*	0.18 _{NS}	-0.31*
2010	0.50**	-0.16 _{NS}	0.28*	-0.17 _{NS}
2005	0.51**	-0.17 _{NS}	0.18 _{NS}	-0.35**
2000	0.52**	-0.31*	0.41**	-0.21*

ns: not significant at $p > 0.05$, *significant at $p \leq 0.05$, **significant at $p \leq 0.01$

3.5 Comparing HQ With and Without Protected Areas

Protected areas are crucial for biodiversity conservation, and their effectiveness was analyzed within the study area by comparing habitat quality (HQ) for specific land covers (forests). The input for protected areas in the model was modified by either including or excluding the protected areas vector file. The change analysis of HQ with and without protected areas for forest cover showed a 10.27% difference. The HQ score with protected areas was 0.56, whereas without protected areas, the forest cover scored only 0.51. This indicates the importance of implementing protected areas to reduce the influence of threat sources on natural

habitats. The study also highlights the effectiveness of the protected areas already implemented in the study area.

3.6 Limitations of the Study

The InVEST habitat quality model, while widely applied in biodiversity conservation and landscape management, still has several limitations [1]. One major limitation is the insufficient spatial and temporal data on species distribution, which is essential for habitat quality studies [10, 27]. Obtaining ecologically acceptable and sufficient information for species distribution across the study area typically requires field-based assessments. Therefore, combining field-based habitat suitability assessments with the InVEST habitat quality model could improve its accuracy [28]. Additionally, the InVEST model does not account for the impacts of soil, climate, vegetation differences, and other abiotic factors that are closely linked to habitat suitability [29]. Different vegetation types and forest edge effects can provide distinct habitat conditions for biodiversity. Furthermore, the model relies heavily on the maximum distance and weighting of threat sources to generate habitat quality scores, which can be influenced by expert judgment and modifications to the input parameters [1,16]. To address these issues, correlation analyses should be conducted to compare model outputs with actual conditions in the study area's habitats. Further research is needed to incorporate more detailed physio-geographical and anthropogenic threat sources to enhance the accuracy of habitat quality simulations using this modeling approach.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study utilized remote sensing and GIS techniques to investigate habitat quality changes within the Johor River Basin over the period 2000–2020. While minor changes in habitat quality scores were observed, there was a significant decline in habitat quality in 2015, with the impacts of climate change and anthropogenic activities being particularly highlighted. The correlation analysis of physio-geographical factors revealed that land elevation influenced the extent of anthropogenic activity in the area. Additionally, the increasing significance of anthropogenic activities on habitat quality indicates that human impacts are increasingly affecting the habitat suitability of the study area. This study underscores how these anthropogenic modifications impact the ecosystem and environment.

In contrast, the positive role of environmental protection efforts in mitigating anthropogenic impacts is also evident in this study. The implementation of protected areas helped reduce habitat degradation, particularly in forest cover

within the study area. To improve overall habitat quality in the Johor River Basin, it is recommended that land management strategies be tailored to address the extent of habitat degradation. A key contribution of this study is that regional habitat quality assessments can serve as guidelines for future policy development and modification. Modeling approaches to habitat quality can assist decision-makers and practitioners in better understanding habitat conditions through visualized outcomes. Ultimately, understanding the role of anthropogenic and abiotic factors in habitat quality will become increasingly important for sustainable development and future human welfare.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.B. Aneseyee, T. Noszczyk, T. Soromessa, E. Elias, "The InVEST Habitat Quality Model Associated with Land Use/Cover Changes: A Qualitative Case Study of the Winike Watershed in the Omo-Gibe Basin, Southwest Ethiopia," *Remote Sens.* 12 (2020) 1103.
- [2] L. Dai, "The influence of land use change on the spatial-temporal variability of habitat quality between 1990 and 2010 in Northeast China," *J. For. Res.* 30 (2019) 2227–2236.
- [3] E.C. Ellis, U. Pascual, O. Mertz, "Ecosystem services and nature's contribution to people: negotiating diverse values and trade-offs in land systems," *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 38 (2019) 86–94.
- [4] A.K. Mashizi, F.J. Escobedo, "Socio-ecological assessment of threats to semi-arid rangeland habitat in Iran using spatial models and actor group opinions," *J. Arid Environ.* 177 (2020) 104136.
- [5] M. Gaglio, M. Lanzoni, G. Nobili, D. Viviani, G. Castaldelli, E.A. Fano, "Ecosystem services approach for sustainable governance in a brackish water lagoon used for aquaculture," *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 62 (2019) 1501–1524.
- [6] X. Zhang, W. Song, Y. Lang, X. Feng, Q. Yuan, J. Wang, "Land use changes in the coastal zone of China's Hebei Province and the corresponding impacts on habitat quality," *Land use policy.* 99 (2020) 104957.
- [7] C.S. Kang, K.D. Kanniah, "Land use and land cover change and its impact on river morphology in Johor River Basin, Malaysia," *J. Hydrol. Reg. Stud.* 41 (2022) 101072.
- [8] Y. Wang, "Impact of climate change on dengue fever epidemics in South and Southeast Asian settings: A modelling study," *Infect. Dis. Model.* 8 (2023) 645–655.
- [9] Y. Yang, P. Li, "Scene-and pixel-level analysis of Landsat cloud coverage and image acquisition probability in South and Southeast Asia," *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.* 123 (2023) 103477.
- [10] J. Zhang, F. Yan, F. Su, V. Lyne, X. Wang, X. Wang, "Response of habitat quality to land use changes in The Johor River Estuary," *Int. J. Digit. Earth.* 17 (2024) 2390439.
- [11] A. Najah, A. Elshafie, O.A. Karim, O. Jaffar, "Prediction of Johor River water quality parameters using artificial neural networks," *Eur. J. Sci. Res.* 28 (2009) 422–435.
- [12] L. Qicai, "Influence of dams on river ecosystem and its countermeasures," *J. Water Resour. Prot.* 2011 (2011).
- [13] X.G. Wang, F.Z. Su, J.J. Zhang, F. Cheng, W.Q. Hu, Z. Ding, "Construction land sprawl and reclamation in the Johor River Estuary of Malaysia since 1973," *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 171 (2019) 87–95.
- [14] J.K. Kazak, J. van Hoof, "Decision support systems for a sustainable management of the indoor and built environment," vol. 27, no. 10. SAGE Publications Sage UK: London, England, 2018, pp. 1303–1306.
- [15] B. Xie, M. Zhang, "Spatio-temporal evolution and driving forces of habitat quality in Guizhou Province," *Sci. Rep.* 13 (2023) 6908.
- [16] M. Terrado, S. Sabater, B. Chaplin-Kramer, L. Mandle, G. Ziv, V. Acuña, "Model development for the assessment of terrestrial and aquatic habitat quality in conservation planning," *Sci. Total Environ.* 540 (2016) 63–70.
- [17] L.T. Beumer, F.M. van Beest, M. Stelvig, N.M. Schmidt, "Spatiotemporal dynamics in habitat suitability of a large Arctic herbivore: Environmental heterogeneity is key to a sedentary lifestyle," *Glob. Ecol. Conserv.* 18 (2019) e00647.
- [18] Z. Niu, "A Process-Based Model Integrating Remote Sensing Data for Evaluating Ecosystem Services," *J. Adv. Model. Earth Syst.* 13 (2021) e2020MS002451.
- [19] X. He, J. Tian, Y. Zhang, Z. Zhao, Z. Cai, Y. Wang, "Attribution and driving force of nitrogen losses from the Taihu Lake Basin by the InVEST and GeoDetector models," *Sci. Rep.* 13 (2023) 7440.
- [20] M.B. Kia, S. Pirasteh, B. Pradhan, A.R. Mahmud, W.N.A. Sulaiman, A. Moradi, "An artificial neural network model for flood simulation using GIS: Johor River Basin, Malaysia," *Environ. Earth Sci.* 67 (2012) 251–264.
- [21] M.L. Tan, A.L. Ibrahim, Z. Yusop, Z. Duan, L. Ling, "Impacts of land-use and climate variability on hydrological components in the Johor River basin, Malaysia," *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 60 (2015) 873–889.
- [22] R. Sharp et al., *InVEST User's Guide.* (2018).
- [23] C. Chen, J. Liu, L. Bi, "Spatial and Temporal Changes of Habitat Quality and Its Influential

- Factors in China Based on the InVEST Model,” *Forests*, 14 (2023) 374.
- [24]F. Tangang, L. Juneng, E. Salimun, A. Jamaluddin, “Scientific understanding of El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and its climatic impacts in Malaysia and surrounding region,” (2019) 5–31.
- [25]H. Heng, W. Pan, J. Siaw Fei Lu, C. Hii, “Coastal and Estuary Reservoir: Case Studies for Johor River Basin,” *J. Civ. Eng. Sci. Technol.* 8 (2017) 25–40.
- [26]M. Hashim et al., “Analysis of Water Yield Changes in the Johor River Basin, Peninsular Malaysia Using Remote Sensing Satellite Imagery,” *Remote Sens.* 15 (2023) 3432.
- [27] S. Polasky, E. Nelson, D. Pennington, and K.A. Johnson, “The impact of land-use change on ecosystem services, biodiversity and returns to landowners: a case study in the state of Minnesota,” *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 48 (2011) 219–242.
- [28]X. Guo, N.C. Coops, P. Tompalski, S.E. Nielsen, C.W. Bater, J.J. Stadt, “Regional mapping of vegetation structure for biodiversity monitoring using airborne lidar data,” *Ecol. Inform.* 38 (2017) 50–61.
- [29]Y. Zhang et al., “Spatial and temporal variability in the net primary production of alpine grassland on the Tibetan Plateau since 1982,” *J. Geogr. Sci.* 24 (2014) 269–287.